

D5.2 – Aviation Noise and Emissions Education Roadmap

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Abstract

PULSAR (Propelling European Leadership through Synergizing Aviation Research) is a Horizon Europe funded project that will inform European policymakers and other stakeholders on future aviation research priorities with the focus on environmental objectives. Future research and innovation achievements are dependent on the availability of relevant education and training to maintain the pipeline of new researchers, scientists and engineers. This report outlines the creation of the new PULSAR European Aviation Education Roadmap that focuses on education and training strategy for topics connected with environmental issues in aviation. The aim of the education roadmap is to enhance awareness and opportunities for early career researchers/scientists/engineers to access higher education courses or continuing professional development training, specifically on topics connected with aviation noise and emissions. Future education and training requirements have been informed by research & innovation stakeholders. The full contents of the PULSAR European Aviation Education Roadmap consists of separate high-level roadmaps for aviation noise and emissions, together with accompanying datasheets. The high-level aviation noise and emissions roadmaps are reproduced in this report. Links are provided to access the datasheets.

Keywords: Aviation noise, Aviation emissions, Environmental impact of aviation, Education and training, Continuing Professional Development, Roadmap

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¹ Use one of the following codes: R=Document, report excluding the periodic and final reports

DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC=Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER=Software, technical diagram, etc.

ORDP=Open Research Data Pilot

²Use one of the following codes: PU=Public, fully open, e.g. web

CO=Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement

CI=Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

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Introduction

PULSAR (Propelling European Leadership through Synergizing Aviation Research) is a Horizon Europe funded project that will inform European policymakers and other stakeholders on future aviation research priorities with the focus on environmental objectives. The key output from PULSAR will be a new European Aviation Research and Innovation Environmental Roadmap that maps a research strategy for environmental aviation research up to 2050.

Future research and innovation achievements are dependent on the availability of relevant education and training to maintain the pipeline of new researchers, scientists and engineers. Linked to the development of the new environmental roadmap is a new PULSAR European Aviation Education Roadmap that will map education and training strategy for topics connected with environmental issues in aviation.

In PULSAR, the education task is WP5.2 called “Education and skills, Gap analysis & connecting R&I with education”. The aim of the education task is to enhance awareness and opportunities for early career researchers/scientists/engineers working at universities, research institutes or industry to access higher education courses or continuing professional development training, specifically on topics connected with aviation noise and emissions. Future education and training requirements will be informed by research & innovation stakeholders.

The education task is lead by the University of Southampton. All the PULSAR partners have contributed to the collection of data for the education task. This report details the methodology used to develop the new education roadmap and outlines the structure of its contents. The full contents of the PULSAR European Aviation Education Roadmap consists of separate high-level roadmaps for aviation noise and emissions, together with accompanying datasheets (in Microsoft Excel format). The high-level aviation noise and emissions roadmaps are reproduced in this report. Links are provided to access the datasheets. Combined this report and the education roadmap datasheets constitute PULSAR deliverable D5.2.

1. Description of work

The workplan for WP5.2 is outlined in this section.

1.1. Identify current education and training opportunities

Compile a database of current subject-specific education and skills-training courses in topics connected with aviation noise and emissions. The survey of current education and training opportunities focuses on postgraduate taught courses delivered by Higher Education Institutes (HEI) and Continuing Professional Development (CPD) training courses delivered by international associations, commercial agencies and professional bodies. Postgraduate taught courses are normally part of master’s level degree programmes (European Qualifications Framework level 7). All the education and training courses should be listed online in the public domain and be delivered by European organisations. Target at least 40 courses with content connected with aviation noise and emissions.

1.2. Identify future education and training requirements

Compile responses from aviation stakeholders on their future requirements for subject-specific education and skills-training courses in topics connected with aviation noise and emissions. Target at least 40 responses from aviation stakeholders.

1.3. Gap analysis and education roadmap

Perform a gap analysis to identify the differences between the requirements of research & innovation stakeholders and current capabilities in education and training in topics connected with aviation noise and emissions.

Use the gap analysis to inform the design of a new education roadmap focussing on education and training connected with environmental issues in aviation. The roadmap will identify the types of subject-specific education and skills-training that is currently available, what is required in the future, and plan timescales and recommendations on how to deliver this education and training.

1.4. Online resource

The data collected for the education roadmap will be used to create a new online resource freely available for all users. This online resource will contain all the information gathered on education and training opportunities connected with topics in environmental aviation. It will be used to promote education and training courses connected with aviation noise and emissions. Additionally, it will help users identify courses, training, and events that are relevant for them.

Tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 have been completed, culminating in the development of the first version of the new PULSAR European Aviation Education Roadmap.

Task 1.4 will be carried out over the next twelve months, with the University of Southampton working with ARC to create a new online resource that contains information on education and training in environmental aviation and published on the [PULSAR website](#). The online resource will be reported in the subsequent deliverable D5.3.

2. Methodology

The methodology for WP5.2, tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3, is outlined in this section.

2.1. Education and training opportunities database

The PULSAR partners have contributed by identifying education and training opportunities connected with topics in aviation noise and emissions. Specifically, this includes courses taught as part of postgraduate taught programmes delivered by HEIs and CPD training courses delivered by other organisations. Postgraduate taught courses are normally part of master's level degree programmes (European Qualifications Framework level 7).

All the information gathered is public domain and available from HEI websites and other websites for international associations, commercial agencies and professional bodies. The information is collated in a set of Microsoft Excel spreadsheets, with the master copies saved on the PULSAR Sharepoint site accessible by all the PULSAR partners.

There are three spreadsheets. (1) Database of education and training connected with topics in aviation noise. (2) Database of education and training connected with topics in aviation emissions. (3) Database reproducing all the information in (1) and (2) ordered by country.

For a course to be included on the database, it must be available within Europe if the delivery method is in-person. Similarly online courses are typically organised by organisations within Europe. Information compiled in the database includes the following:

1. Name of course
2. Organisation
3. Location and Country
4. Information on course contents
5. Credit (or non-credit bearing)
6. Qualification level
7. Availability of training (and any pre-requisites)
8. In-person, hybrid or online
9. Language of instruction
10. Duration (and dates if known)
11. Cost
12. Webpage link

A screenshot showing part of the master spreadsheet (3) is shown in Figure 1. This version of the spreadsheet orders the courses by country. Each country has a separate tab. (In Figure 1 the tab for France is shown.)

5	Name of training opportunity	Information added by:	Type of training opportunity	Topic of training (Noise/Emissions /Both)	Contact person	Information on training contents	Credit or non-credit training	Qualification level	Who can attend the training?	Pre-requisite knowledge / qualifications	In-person, online or hybrid
6	Aeroacoustics	Vincent Jaunet	Part of MSc Acoustical and Vibration Engineering	Noise	Eduardo Martini, MCF ISAE-ENSMA, eduardo.martini@isae-ensma.fr	Basic knowledge to grasp the specific difficulties in solving problems in aeroacoustics; such as sound generation and propagation by and in turbulent flow, characteristics of the acoustic emission of aircraft turbojets for example. Physic interpretation of underlying mechanisms and an introduction to the standard estimation models of convection and refraction effects associated with the propagation of acoustic waves in shear and non isothermal flows, and of generation of sound due to turbulent fluctuations (aeroacoustics analogy).	1.5 ECTS	Master 2	ISAE-ENSMA Students	Relevant undergraduate degree (to be accepted onto the MSc programme)	In-person
	Aerodynamically		Course: Part of a MSc in Acoustics & Part of Curriculum in Engineering		Professors Marc C. Jacob and	The physical mechanisms of aerodynamic sound generation. Aeroacoustic analogies. Radiation of moving sources and surfaces. Jet noise, Airframe		2nd Year MSc Students in Acoustics, Fluid dynamics, PhD students, young	Students registered in the MSc Acoustics (Lyon) and Engineering degree (ECL) - Local PhD students and	Background in Unsteady Aerodynamics, Turbulence, Acoustics, Engineering	

Figure 1: Screen shot of the PULSAR education and training opportunities database

A target of at least 40 courses with content connected with aviation noise and emissions was a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) in the PULSAR proposal. Currently a total of 85 courses are listed on the database, although this is by no means an exhaustive list. The main difficulty encountered during the

data collection phase is that content connected with aviation noise and emissions is available across a range of engineering and science degree programmes.

For topics connected with aviation noise, the discipline subject areas in acoustics/acoustical engineering cover a lot of the relevant physical sciences, and psychoacoustics/sound perception cover some of the relevant human sciences.

For topics connected with aviation emissions, relevant discipline subject areas are more disparate. For example, combustion is included in chemical engineering, atmospheric physics includes meteorology and geophysical fluid dynamics, climate change is linked environmental science and so on.

The approach followed on PULSAR was to focus on education and training predominantly linked to aeronautical engineering-based degree programmes (and to a lesser extent acoustical engineering). More broad courses on, for example, climate science/climate change, have not been included in the database, because the focus is not aeronautical engineering, and aviation is only one of many sources of emissions that contribute to air pollution and climate change.

Furthermore, owing to the wide range of topics that are linked to aviation noise and emissions, keyword searches on search engines only gave limited results that were relevant. Instead, local knowledge of the PULSAR partners was valuable, signposting to relevant education and training in specific countries. With recent rapid advances in Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI), in the future this may provide an improved search-based tool compared to a traditional search engine.

2.2. Stakeholder consultation on future education and training requirements

Aviation stakeholders have been consulted to give their views on future requirements for subject-specific education and skills-training courses in topics connected with aviation noise and emissions. The principal method to obtain feedback from aviation stakeholders was via an online questionnaire that was hosted on the EU Survey platform (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/>). Since the stakeholder consultation involved data collection from human participants, before starting it was necessary to obtain ethics approval from the University of Southampton (since the work was carried out by staff from UoS). Ethics approval for this work involved how information about the questionnaire was provided to the participants, how consent was obtained, what the data would be used for and how the data would be stored. It was decided that the questionnaire should be anonymous. This simplified the ethics approval process and eased requirements related to data protection legislation since no personal data that could identify the participant would be collected (and by extension no personal data would be stored).

Using an anonymous survey meant that a combined participant information sheet and consent form could be used. Since the questionnaire was online, prospective participants had to read the participant information sheet and tick the consent form before they could access the questionnaire.

Ethics approval was granted by the University of Southampton for the “EU Project PULSAR – Education Roadmap Questionnaire”, submitter name: Alan McAlpine, date: 18th April 2024, submission ID: 93269. A full copy of the combined participant information sheet and consent form and the Education Roadmap questionnaire is reproduced in the Appendix. Participants were advised not to include any personal information in their answers that could identify them.

Two screen shots showing parts of the questionnaire as it appeared on the EU Survey platform are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2: Screen shot of the PULSAR Education Roadmap questionnaire (Start page)

Figure 3: Screen shot of the PULSAR Education Roadmap questionnaire (Page 3/8)

Responses to the questionnaire were collated between June and December 2024. Stakeholders were informed about the Education task in PULSAR in a variety of ways. Presentations and discussion on the Education roadmap were included at PULSAR workshops on 11th October 2023, Budapest and 24th October 2024, Bucharest. Both these PULSAR workshops were held in conjunction with the annual CEAS-ASC workshop. Additionally, all the PULSAR partners communicated to relevant contacts a message and weblink for the questionnaire. ARC as part of the PULSAR communication activities promoted the questionnaire on the PULSAR website, on social media (LinkedIn) and via the ARC newsletter.

The target of at least 40 responses from aviation stakeholders was achieved, but this took nearly six months. All the responses were downloaded from the EU survey website and archived in a master Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. Following the guidance from the ethics approval, the responses are stored on a secure password-protected storage drive. The responses will be stored for at least ten years.

The data collection in tasks 1.1 and 1.2 was used to develop the new PULSAR Education roadmap, informed by a gap analysis. Details of the methodology are in the next section.

2.3. Development of the PULSAR education roadmap

The PULSAR education roadmap was developed using a “gap analysis” that is a common methodology in project management. In general, a gap analysis compares the current state with a target future state and identifies the “gaps” between the two states. Having identified the gaps, an action plan or strategy may be developed to plan how to fill the gaps and transition the current state to the desired future state.

For the development of the education roadmap, the gap analysis process is summarised in four steps:

1. Current state Evaluation of current education and training opportunities connected with aviation noise and emissions gathered in the PULSAR education and training opportunities database (see sections 1.1 and 2.1).
2. Future state Requirements for future education and training connected with aviation noise and emissions gathered via aviation stakeholder responses to an online questionnaire (see sections 1.2 and 2.2).
3. Gap analysis Having gathered the responses from the questionnaire, these were checked for incomplete or missing data. All the responses were archived in a single Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. The first task was to categorise the key future requirements. Initially, a GenAI tool was used to search for patterns and to assist with a first categorisation. Then, the categorisation was refined by reading all the answers. Since all the answers to the questionnaire were in free form text, the use of GenAI proved less useful compared to analysing the data by reading the responses to identify key future requirements. More details on the categorisation are provided in section 3. The second task was to map the different categories onto all the entries in the current education and training opportunities database. This enabled the gap analysis to be carried out, by identifying the categories listed in the future requirements that were not covered by the current education and training opportunities.
4. Action plan Using the outcomes from the gap analysis, the PULSAR education roadmap is the action plan that has been developed to inform education and training providers and other relevant stakeholders on the current state and future vision to develop education and training connected with aviation noise and emissions from 2025 up to 2050. The maturity of education

and training in a specific category is rated by using a new scale, called the ETRL (Education & Training Readiness Level) that is inspired by the TRL (Technology Readiness Level) scale used by industry. More details on the proposed ETRL scale and the structure of the education roadmap are provided in section 3.

2.4. Online resource

As stated in section 1.4, the data collected for the education roadmap will be used to create a new online resource that will promote education and training opportunities connected with topics in environmental aviation. The online resource will be created over the next twelve months and reported in the subsequent deliverable D5.3. An example of an online resource that promotes degree programmes in acoustics is provided by the European Acoustics Association (EAA). A screenshot from their webpage is shown in Figure 4. The EEA webpage shows an interactive map of Europe with degree programmes listed by country. This type of webpage is an example of the type of online resource that is envisioned for this task in the PULSAR project.

Figure 4: Screenshot from <https://euracoustic.org/scholar/>

3. PULSAR European Aviation Education Roadmap

3.1. Categorisation of future education and training requirements

An example of a categorisation used for training in higher education is provided by the VITAE Researcher Development Framework (<https://vitae.ac.uk/vitae-researcher-development-framework/>). In this example, the training is research and transferable skills training for postgraduate students. The Researcher Development Framework identifies four broad domains connected with researcher development that are shown in Figure 5. Each domain is then split into sub-domains that group

together related categories of skills training with details provided, as shown in Figure 6. This type of categorisation by domains and sub-domains is an ideal template for the PULSAR education roadmap.

Figure 5: Vitae Researcher Development Framework, domains A to D. Reproduced from <https://vitae.ac.uk/researcher-development-framework/>

Figure 6: Vitae Researcher Development Framework, sub-domains with details of each category. Reproduced from <https://vitae.ac.uk/researcher-development-framework/>

For the PULSAR education roadmap, informed by the data collected from the aviation stakeholder questionnaire, four high-level domains are identified: Physical Sciences, Human Sciences, Future Technology and Aviation Regulations, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: High-level domains for the PULSAR education roadmap

Owing to the different topics identified for education and training connected with aviation noise or emissions, the sub-domains are slightly different for noise or emissions. The sub-domains for Physical Sciences are shown in Figure 8.

(a) Noise

(b) Emissions

Figure 8: Sub-domains for the Physical Sciences (a) Noise and (b) Emissions

The full categorisation for noise and emissions are detailed in the high-level versions of the PULSAR education roadmaps shown in sections 3.4 and 3.5.

3.2. Education and Training Readiness Level (ETRL)

Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) are a metric commonly used in research and innovation to assess the maturity of a technology. The TRL used by industry normally has nine levels from TRL1 to TRL9. TRL1 is “basic principles” whilst TRL9 is “operations” (when a new technology is brought to market). The use of TRL markers as part of the strategy for future research and innovation is standard practice. Accordingly, for the new PULSAR education roadmap, a new metric scale is proposed called the Education and Training Readiness Level (ETRL) to assess the maturity level of provision of education and training.

It is noted that similarly named “Education Readiness Levels (ERLs)” previously have been developed by Dinda, Simpson and Gluck (2017)³. Despite the similarity in the acronyms – both of which were chosen to align with the generic “readiness level” terminology used by other scales – the proposed ETRL used in the current work is very different to the ERLs. Specifically, in the current work, the purpose of the ETRL is to assess the maturity of provision of education and training in a specific discipline within Europe. Contrastingly, in the previous work by Dinda *et al.*, the purpose of the ERLs is for comparison of two or more educational courses or modules. For a specific course or module, a score between 0 and 10 is assigned to each of the following elements: class size, cost, instructors, depth of facilities, target audience and course material. Then a graphical representation is used to compare courses or modules using the ERLs.

Returning to the current work, the proposed Education and Training Readiness Level (ETRL) scale is based on “The AAAQ Framework”. The framework was originally developed in the healthcare sector, but it is designed to be a general tool for assessing all types of public services (see for example <https://www.humanrights.dk/publications/aaaq-framework-right-water-international-indicators>).

The AAAQ framework covers the Availability, Accessibility, Aceptability and Quality of a public service. In PULSAR, this framework has been applied to education and training with the suggested indicators for each category summarised in Table 1.⁴

³ Shantanab Dinda, Timothy W. Simpson & Leanne Gluck (2017). ‘Education Readiness Levels (ERLs): A scale for assessing educational coursework and training modules.’ *Proceedings of the ASME 2017 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference*. Paper No. DETC2017-68086. IDETC/CIE 2017, 6-9 August, Cleveland, Ohio. DOI: 10.1115/DETC2017-68086.

⁴ Authors’ note. Although we were unable to find a specific reference on the AAAQ framework applied to public education, we would be surprised if this is the first time the AAAQ toolbox has been used to assess education.

AAAQ framework applied to education and training	
Availability	Refers to the existence of education/training opportunities. Includes quantity and type.
Accessibility	Refers to multiple components including physical (location of education/training), financial (fees to access education/training), administrative (conditions to access education/training e.g. registration requirements such as accredited prior learning, previous qualifications, language requirements), social (non-discrimination in provision of education/training or are groups excluded, for example, by nationality), information (how is information on an education/training opportunities disseminated).
Acceptability	Refers to multiple components including whether an education/training opportunity is respectful of EDI (equality, diversity and inclusion) and whether an education/training opportunity is respectful of ethical and professional standards.
Quality	Refers to the quality of the education/training opportunities and how this is monitored (quality assurance). Do the service providers have the necessary skills and experience? Is the environment appropriate with the necessary facilities. Are appropriate Health and Safety measures in place. Is there support (academic, pastoral) available to users. What is the overall quality of the experience. Are there appropriate quality assurance measures in place to ensure the quality of the provision of education/training.

Table 1: Availability, Accessibility, Acceptability and Quality framework applied to education and training courses

On applying the AAAQ framework to education and training, the proposed ETRL maturity scale is shown in Figure 9. The scale is from 1 to 7. ETRL1 indicates there are no education or training opportunities available, whilst ETRL7 indicates there are widespread education or training opportunities, with few accessibility conditions, easy to find public domain information, and quality assurance processes that ensure the acceptability and quality of the education or training.

The ETRL is used as part of the detailed PULSAR education roadmap datasheets. The structure of the PULSAR education roadmap is described in the next section.

Level	Education & Training Readiness Level (ETRL)
1	No availability of education/training in Europe.
2	Limited availability of education/training in Europe (only 1 or 2 countries). Fees/charges to access education/training can be high. Conditions to access education/training can be major. Availability of public domain information can be limited.
3	Limited availability of education/training in Europe (only 1 or 2 countries). Fees/charges to access education/training are normally low. Conditions to access education/training are normally minor. Easy to find public domain information, despite limited availability of education/training. Normally the education/training has quality assurance processes to ensure acceptability and quality.
4	Moderate availability of education/training in Europe (between 3 to 5 countries). Fees/charges to access education/training are variable (low to high). Conditions to access education/training are variable (minor to major). Availability of public domain information can be mixed. Some of the education/training has quality assurance processes to ensure acceptability and quality.
5	Moderate availability of education/training in Europe (between 3 to 5 countries). Fees/charges to access education/training are commonly low. Conditions to access education/training are commonly minor. Easy to find public domain information, commonly available in more than one language. Normally the education/training has quality assurance processes to ensure acceptability and quality of education/training.
6	Widespread availability of education/training in Europe (more than 5 countries). Fees/charges to access education/training are variable (low to high). Conditions to access education/training are variable (minor to major). Public domain information available but not always in multiple languages. Some of the education/training has quality assurance processes to ensure acceptability and quality.
7	Widespread availability of education/training in Europe (more than 5 countries). Fees/charges to access education/training are normally low. Conditions to access education/training are normally minor. Easy to find public domain information, available in multiple languages. Education/training has quality assurance processes to ensure acceptability and quality.

Figure 9: Education & Training Readiness Level (ETRL) used in the PULSAR education roadmap

3.3. Structure of the PULSAR education roadmap

Roadmaps for aviation noise strategy were an integral part of work by the X-Noise network, and more recently on the EU project ANIMA (Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, grant agreement no. 769627). On PULSAR the aim is to broaden the scope of the roadmapping activity, to develop a new European Aviation Research and Innovation Environmental Roadmap, and in parallel a new European Aviation Education Roadmap.

For continuity, the structure of the ANIMA roadmaps is used for the new education roadmap. On ANIMA a set of high-level roadmaps were developed that are available in the public domain. Accompanying each high-level roadmap, there is a more detailed datasheet that includes information on the following:

1. Current status
2. Vision
3. Target maturity level at end of period (TRL)
4. Related projects

The ANIMA datasheets are not available in the public domain.

Examples of a high-level roadmap and accompanying datasheet from the ANIMA project are shown in Figures 10 and 11. The high-level roadmaps identify domains and sub-domains for each topic. The datasheets provide detailed information for each sub-domain.

For the PULSAR education roadmap, the high-level roadmaps for noise and emissions identify the relevant domains and sub-domains to categorise current and future requirements for education and training connected with environmental aviation. These high-level roadmaps are shown in sections 3.4 and 3.5. The information in the high-level education roadmaps is presented following the circular template used by the Vitae Researcher Development Framework (see Figure 6), which differs to the presentation of the ANIMA high-level roadmaps (see Figure 10).

Additionally, for the PULSAR education roadmaps detailed datasheets are included to accompany the high-level roadmaps. These datasheets are presented in the same format as the ANIMA roadmap datasheets, with some necessary adjustments in the information provided. For the PULSAR education roadmaps, the detailed datasheets include information on the following:

1. Current status
2. Vision
3. Target maturity level at end of period (ETRL)
4. Examples of education/training opportunities

The PULSAR education roadmaps detailed datasheets are written in Microsoft Excel. Separate roadmap datasheets are provided for aviation noise and aviation emissions.

Figure 10: ANIMA high-level roadmap for Technology Development

Technology Development		
Near-term integration of ultra-high speed turbofan propulsion system		
Advanced nacelle acoustic technology		
Current status	<p>With engine ultra-high speed and low noise levels, it is necessary to explore the use of nacelle technology to reduce noise, reduce engine noise and reduce the noise footprint. To develop the technology, research has already started some years ago, and some of them are already being tested.</p>	Track
Water Research Goal (%)	<p>Although some test experiments are still needed to refine the design, the main activities for defining these technologies are being carried out. Significant progress is being made in the development of noise reduction technologies. Significant progress is being made in the development of noise reduction technologies. Significant progress is being made in the development of noise reduction technologies.</p>	
Advanced flow physics simulation application to fan & turbomachinery		
Current status	<p>Computational fluid dynamics methods for aerodynamics have been the subject of high investment in the past, with increasing progress. This application to the high-complexity areas of fan and turbomachinery, turbofan engines, is a challenge.</p>	Track
Water Research Goal (%)	<p>CFD methods will be needed for the aerodynamic design of fan geometries of turbofan engines, and for the analysis of fan noise. The need for further development and validation is being addressed. This will be the subject of research activities across increasing complexity of flow, especially for CFD. Advances will include improved, more realistic engine CFD and CFD for CFD. The current approach is based on CFD, but the challenge is to apply CFD to the complex, multi-scale, multi-physics problems of fan and turbomachinery. The approach will be to use CFD to model the flow, and then use CFD to model the noise.</p>	
Integrated low emission combustors		
Current status	<p>With the appearance of low emission combustors, the technology for engine combustion combustion has been significantly improved. It is now possible to use high speed tests to provide sufficient data for combustion and noise. Further development of advanced methods for combustion and noise reduction is being carried out.</p>	Track
Water Research Goal (%)	<p>Combustion, modeling and testing of low emission combustors has been a complex task. It is being addressed. Significant progress is being made in the development of low emission combustors. Significant progress is being made in the development of low emission combustors. Significant progress is being made in the development of low emission combustors.</p>	
AI / Airframe interaction mitigation		
Current status	<p>An active need to reduce noise with increasing fan speed. This will require a significant noise reduction effort, especially for the low speed effects. An active need to reduce noise with increasing fan speed. This will require a significant noise reduction effort, especially for the low speed effects.</p>	Track
Water Research Goal (%)	<p>AI methods are being used to reduce noise with increasing fan speed. This will require a significant noise reduction effort, especially for the low speed effects. An active need to reduce noise with increasing fan speed. This will require a significant noise reduction effort, especially for the low speed effects.</p>	

Figure 11: ANIMA datasheet roadmap for Technology Development. (Image is blurred intentionally because the content is classed as “confidential”.)

3.4. High-level PULSAR education roadmap for aviation noise

Figure 12 shows the new high-level PULSAR education roadmap for aviation noise. The choice of domains and sub-domains are informed by the responses of the aviation stakeholders to the PULSAR education questionnaire. In the accompanying datasheet, each sub-domain has its own section with more detailed information on the current status and the vision to increase the ETRL. The aviation noise datasheet can be accessed at <https://zenodo.org/records/16357118>

Figure 12: High-level PULSAR education roadmap for aviation noise

3.5. High-level PULSAR education roadmap for aviation emissions

Figure 13 shows the new high-level PULSAR education roadmap for aviation emissions. Where possible the choice of domains and sub-domains are the same or similar to the aviation noise roadmap. For example, there are comparable sub-domains on “noise control systems” or “emissions control systems”, and “community noise annoyance” or “community response to emissions”. Again, in the accompanying datasheet, each sub-domain has its own section with more detailed information on the current status and the vision to increase the ETRL. The aviation emissions datasheet can be accessed at <https://zenodo.org/records/16356085>

Figure 13: High-level PULSAR education roadmap for aviation emissions

4. Quantitative results from the data collection

Quantitative results from the data collection are summarised in this section.

4.1. Education and training opportunities database

Figure 14 is a map of Europe showing all the countries surveyed for the PULSAR education and training opportunities database.

Figure 15 shows the percentage breakdown by country of the entries in the PULSAR education and training opportunities database.

Figure 16 shows the percentage breakdown by topic of the entries in the PULSAR education and training opportunities database.

There is a significant imbalance between the number of courses on noise compared to the number of courses on emissions. As noted in section 2.1, for topics connected with aviation noise, there are discipline subject areas in acoustics/acoustical engineering that cover a lot of the relevant physical sciences, and some of the relevant human sciences. Contrastingly, for topics connected with aviation emissions, relevant discipline subject areas are more disparate.

Interactive Map of Europe, taken from <https://philarcher.org/diary/2013/euomap/> and distributed under the creative Commons licence <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/deed.en>

Figure 14: Map of Europe showing the countries surveyed for the PULSAR education and training opportunities database

Figure 15: Percentage breakdown of number of entries by country in the PULSAR education and training opportunities database

Figure 16: Percentage breakdown of number of entries by topic in the PULSAR education and training opportunities database

4.2. Education roadmap questionnaire

Figures 17 and 18 show respectively a map and percentage breakdown by country of the responses by aviation stakeholders to the PULSAR education questionnaire.

Figure 19 shows the percentage breakdown by type of organisation of the responses by aviation stakeholders to the PULSAR education questionnaire. There was an excellent response rate from stakeholders working at research centres and HEIs, but disappointingly the percentage response rate

from stakeholders working in the aerospace industry was low despite widespread promotion of the survey.

Interactive Map of Europe, taken from <https://philarcher.org/diary/2013/euromap/> and distributed under the creative Commons licence <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/deed.en>

Figure 17: Map of Europe showing the countries where stakeholders that responded to PULSAR education questionnaire are located

Figure 18: Percentage breakdown of number of responses by country to the PULSAR education questionnaire

Figure 19: Percentage breakdown of number of responses by type of organisation to the PULSAR education questionnaire

Tables 2 and 3 show, respectively for aviation noise and aviation emissions topics, the percentage breakdown by domain recommended by aviation stakeholders to be delivered either by HEIs or other organisations. The category “Higher Education Institutes” is restricted to universities only. The category “other organisations” includes all other providers of education and training courses such as professional bodies, research and technology organisations, international associations or commercial agencies. For each category, the percentage breakdown indicates stakeholders’ expectations of the split between the domains of the total education and training provision.

For example, taking HEIs, 41% (noise) and 49% (emissions) of all the topics recommended to be delivered by university courses are classed within the physical sciences domain, but only 16% (noise) and 15% (emissions) of all topics are classed within the aviation regulations domain. Contrastingly, taking other organisations, 3% (noise) and 9% (emissions) of all the topics recommended to be delivered by training courses are classed within the physical sciences domain, whereas 60% (noise) and 67% (emissions) of all topics are classed within the aviation regulations domain. These examples show a clear delineation between delivery of education and training by HEIs or other organisations. Overwhelming teaching of physical sciences is expected to be delivered by HEIs, whereas training on aviation regulations is expected to be delivered by other organisations such as professional bodies.

For the other domains (human sciences and future technology) there is less obvious delineation between the delivery of education and training by HEIs or other organisations. This indicates that stakeholders’ expectations for the delivery of education and training in human sciences and future technology does not prioritise one type of delivery as the preferred approach. Topics within the human sciences or future technology domains are expected to be delivered by both university courses and professional development training courses.

Aviation Noise	Higher Education Institutes	Other organisations e.g. professional bodies
Physical Sciences	41%	3%
Human Sciences	23%	24%
Future Technology	20%	13%
Aviation regulations	16%	60%

Table 2: Percentage breakdown by domain of aviation noise topics recommended to be delivered by HEIs or other organisations

Aviation Emissions	Higher Education Institutes	Other organisations e.g. professional bodies
Physical Sciences	49%	9%
Human Sciences	10%	5%
Future Technology	26%	19%
Aviation regulations	15%	67%

Table 3: Percentage breakdown by domain of aviation emissions topics recommended to be delivered by HEIs or other organisations

Finally, Table 4 shows for aviation noise and aviation emissions topics, the current percentage breakdown by domain of educational courses delivered by HEIs (based on the PULSAR education and training opportunities database). Currently for both noise and emissions roughly half of all educational courses delivered by HEIs are in the physical sciences. This tallies closely with the recommended breakdown by aviation stakeholders for delivery of topics in physical sciences by HEIs.

Comparable data for the current percentage breakdown by domain of training courses delivered by other organisations is not included owing to the smaller sample size of this type of courses in the PULSAR education and training opportunities database.

	Aviation Noise	Aviation Emissions
Physical Sciences	51%	49%
Human Sciences	10%	10%
Future Technology	14%	26%
Aviation regulations	25%	15%

Table 4: Percentage breakdown by domain of aviation noise and aviation emissions education currently delivered by HEIs (listed in the PULSAR database)

5. Key findings and recommendations

The key findings and recommendations from the new PULSAR European Aviation Education Roadmap are listed below⁵:

- The study of aviation noise and emissions spans multiple disciplines.
- In the physical sciences, key areas include acoustics, aeroacoustics, signal processing, combustion physics, atmospheric physics, and climate science.
- From the human sciences perspective, important fields include community responses to noise and emissions, psychoacoustics, and the health impacts associated with both.
- Future technological developments relevant to this field include the integration of Artificial Intelligence, as well as innovative design and control systems aimed at reducing noise and emissions.
- Aviation regulations encompass policies, environmental monitoring, and regulatory standards related to noise and emissions.
- Stakeholders generally expect HEIs to lead the delivery of education in physical science disciplines, while training on aviation regulations is primarily expected from other organisations.
- Stakeholders generally expect HEIs to lead the delivery of education in human sciences and future technology, but with other organisations also delivering related training associated with both.
- Specialised master's degree programmes in acoustical engineering that cover a broad range of physical science topics relevant to aviation noise are available.
- Beyond specialised acoustical engineering degrees, acoustics and signal processing are widely taught across various engineering and science master's programmes.
- Aeroacoustics is taught in some engineering master's programmes, but no dedicated degree programme currently exists.
- The ETRL for physical science topics relevant to aviation noise can be raised by the introduction of a specialised degree in aeroacoustics, and through training courses incorporating acoustics, aeroacoustics and signal processing content.
- Specialised master's degree programmes that cover a broad range of physical science topics relevant to aviation emissions are not available.
- Combustion physics, atmospheric physics, and climate science are widely taught in engineering and science master's programmes such as chemical engineering, meteorology, and environmental science, but are rarely integrated into a single programme or included in aeronautical engineering degrees.
- The ETRL for physical science topics relevant to aviation emissions can be significantly raised by introducing the key topics as part of the curriculum of aeronautical engineering degrees, and through training courses incorporating content on the environmental effects of aviation.
- Specialised master's degree programmes that cover a broad range of human science topics relevant to aviation noise and emissions are not available.

⁵ This list is a summary of the key findings and recommendations taken from the aviation noise and emissions datasheets that accompany the high-level education roadmaps.

- Psychoacoustics is taught in some acoustics and audiology master's programmes.
- Health impact of pollution (noise and emissions) is taught in some master's programmes such as environmental science but generally the content is not specifically on the environmental impact of aviation.
- The ETRL for human science topics relevant to aviation noise and emissions can be significantly raised by introducing the key topics as part of the curriculum of aeronautical engineering degrees, and through training courses that link content on community exposure, quality of life and health impacts with relevant aviation regulations.
- Specialised master's degree programmes that cover a broad range of future technology topics relevant to aviation noise and emissions are not available.
- Machine Learning (computers learning autonomously) and generative Artificial Intelligence (computers generating new content that mimics humans) is widely taught at master's level within the computer science discipline, but not yet in aeronautical programmes specifically on mitigating aviation's environmental impact.
- Topics on innovative design and control linked to aviation noise and emissions are taught in some engineering master's programmes.
- The ETRL for future technology topics relevant to aviation noise and emissions can be significantly raised by inclusion as part of the curriculum of aeronautical engineering degrees advances in AI integration with engineering design focused on reducing the environmental impact of aviation. Target high ETRL owing to rapid development and accessibility of GenAI.
- There is significant potential for master's engineering programmes and short courses to raise the ETRL for future technology topics by incorporating content on mitigating aviation's environmental impact through innovative design and control strategies, such as novel propulsion systems (hybrid, electric), and sustainable aviation fuels, integrated into design of future air vehicles.
- Some master's degree programmes include content on policy, monitoring and standards for aviation noise and emissions. Environmental monitoring is the most common topic covered by degree programmes.
- The ETRL for aviation regulations relevant to noise and emissions can be significantly raised by expanding specialist training delivered by other organisations. Recommended topics include policies and standards for future air vehicles such as urban air mobility and UAVs, regulations for sustainable fuels and novel propulsion systems, and environmental monitoring of airport noise and emissions.

6. Concluding remarks

Topics connected with aviation noise and emissions span a range of content and disciplines. The degree programmes delivered by HEIs that feature in the education and training opportunities database typically cover content that is focussed on one domain. This is not surprising: the content in a degree in a physical science tends not to significantly overlap with the content in a degree in a human science. Nevertheless, to have a holistic view and understanding of the environmental impact of aviation, it is necessary to have some knowledge and understanding of the connections between the generation and control of aviation noise and emissions, the physiological and psychological impact of aviation noise and emissions, and how regulations can be used to balance competing needs that can reduce the environmental impact of aviation through future technological advances alongside ongoing growth in aviation. Thus, a key observation, particularly connected with the delivery of aeronautical-based degree programmes, is the challenge to improve the cross-disciplinary nature of the educational offering. For example, advances in computer science through Generative Artificial Intelligence have the potential to transform some aspects of traditional engineering design. Also, for example, advances in climate science should inform priority targets for future propulsion systems and fuels.

Training courses can provide more cross-disciplinary content, albeit they are not normally designed to cover content in the same depth compared to degree programmes. Nevertheless, another key observation is that gaps in content provision by HEIs can be filled by bespoke training courses that focus on the environmental impact of aviation. The key example is that training courses more commonly cover topics connected with aviation regulations with some cross-disciplinary content linked to physical and/or human sciences.

Finally, the new PULSAR education roadmap does not incorporate an exhaustive list of all education and training opportunities across Europe connected with aviation noise and emissions. It is not feasible to identify and catalogue all courses delivered by HEIs across the range of relevant disciplines or even restricting the search to aeronautical-based degree programmes. However, this is the first version of a strategy-based roadmap for future education and training focussed on the environmental impact of aviation. The new PULSAR education roadmap is not a static document, and the database of education and training opportunities can be updated. The purpose, as well as formally developing a strategy for future education/training direction and provision, is to enhance awareness of education and training opportunities to attract future scientists and engineers to research and innovate technological solutions to reduce the environmental impact of aviation.

Appendix 1. PULSAR Education Roadmap Questionnaire

Combined Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form for Anonymous Online Surveys for Adult Participants

Study Title: Environmental aviation survey on educational requirements for early career employees in the civil aviation sector

Lead researcher: Professor Alan McAlpine, Institute of Sound and Vibration Research, University of Southampton

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Ethics no: ERGO/FEPS/93269

Version and date: V8 18 April 2024

Aim of the study

Survey of stakeholders in the civil aviation sector to identify education and training requirements in aircraft noise and emissions looking forward to 2050. The aim is to identify the key areas of education and training in aircraft noise and emissions that are currently available and what new requirements are needed.

What is the research about?

[PULSAR](#) (Propelling eUropean Leadership through Synergizing Aviation Research) is a new European Union project with the purpose of consolidating a European research and innovation roadmap in the field of environmental aviation, specifically focussed on civil aviation noise and emissions. PULSAR has received funding from the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101095395. The PULSAR partners are: ONERA (project leader), SAFRAN Aircraft Engines, Airbus, DLR, NLR, ANOTEC, Airport Regions Council, Erdyn Consultants, Manchester Metropolitan University, Rolls–Royce plc, Rolls–Royce Deutschland and the University of Southampton.

Citizens and stakeholders are more and more concerned about the environmental impact of civil aviation. The PULSAR consortium will develop an environmental aviation education roadmap to guide the strategic direction of future education and training courses in the field of aviation noise and emissions. Work on the education roadmap is being led by the University of Southampton (lead researcher [Professor Alan McAlpine](#)). Current provision and future requirements of subject-specific education and training in aviation noise and emissions will be identified, and a gap analysis used to develop the new PULSAR education roadmap. The roadmap will identify the subject-specific educational courses and skills-training that is required, and plan how to deliver this training within specified timescales.

As part of the development of the PULSAR education roadmap, you are invited to participate in this study.

What will happen to me if I take part?

This study involves completing an anonymous questionnaire which should take approximately 15 minutes of your time. If you are happy to complete this survey, you will need to tick (check) the box to show your consent. As this survey is anonymous, the research team will not be able to know whether you have participated, or what answers you provided.

This study has been approved by the Faculty Research Ethics Committee (FREC) at the University of Southampton (Ethics Number: ERGO/FEPS/93269).

Why have I been asked to participate?

The PULSAR consortium is seeking to connect with research and innovation stakeholders in the civil aviation sector to acquire information on future education and skills-training requirements for early career researchers, scientists or engineers seeking to work in the field of aviation noise and emissions.

PULSAR is aiming to select around 50 people and organisations for this study.

What information will be collected?

The questionnaire is anonymous, and no personal data is requested.

The questions in this survey ask for inputs from policy makers and employers in the civil aviation sector who recruit graduates/early career workers. Information will be collected on the educational and skills-training in the field of aviation noise and emissions that employers are seeking in their new employees (either before they are recruited or training available for continuing professional development).

Some of the survey questions contain textboxes where you will be asked to type in your own answers. Please note that for this survey to be anonymous, you should not include in your answers any information from which you, or other people, could be identified.

You do not have to answer all the questions if you do not wish to do so.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

If you decide to take part in this study, you will not receive any direct benefits; however, your participation will provide information to contribute to the development of the education roadmap on aviation noise and emissions for delivery to the European Commission.

What will happen to the information collected?

All information collected for this study will be stored securely on a password-protected computer and backed up on a secure server. Only the research team will have access to this information.

The information collected will be analysed and used to inform the development of PULSAR education roadmap. The information included on the education roadmap will be published on the PULSAR website to promote this work.

The University of Southampton conducts research to the highest standards of ethics and research integrity. In accordance with our Research Data Management Policy, data will be held for 10 years after the study has finished when it will be securely destroyed.

What happens if there is a problem?

If you are unhappy about any aspect of this study and would like to make a formal complaint, you can contact the Head of Research Integrity and Governance, University of Southampton, on the following contact details: Email: rgoinfo@soton.ac.uk, phone: + 44 2380 595058.

Please quote the Ethics number above. Please note that by making a complaint you might be no longer anonymous.

More information on your rights as a study participant is available via this link:
<https://www.southampton.ac.uk/about/governance/participant-information.page>

Thank you for reading this information sheet and considering taking part in this research.

How to take part?

If you decide to take part in the online survey, please click here.

Education Roadmap Questionnaire

- Please tick (check) this box to indicate that you have read and understood the information sheet and are aged 18 or over and agree to take part in this survey. Please do not include any personal data or identifiable information in your responses to the survey.

1. Type of Company/Organisation

Select one from: Research and Technology Organisation, Higher Education, Aerospace industry, SME, Professional body, Other.

2. Location in Europe

Please state the European country where you work.

3. Future education requirements in aviation noise

Consider research and development in aviation noise and the education/training requirements that are likely to be needed in the future (up to 2050). Please list suggestions of key educational topics that you would expect to be delivered by university postgraduate courses. For example, this could include courses on theoretical subjects, data analysis, experimental techniques, or computational modelling. Please include both established topics (that will still be needed in the future) and new topics.

4. Future training requirements in aviation noise

Following question 3, please list suggestions of key training requirements that you would expect to be provided by international associations, commercial agencies, or professional bodies. For example, this could include continuing professional development training courses on policy, legislation, or certification.

5. Future education requirements in aviation emissions

Consider research and development in aviation emissions and the education/training requirements that are likely to be needed in the future (up to 2050). Please list suggestions of key educational subjects that could be provided by university postgraduate courses. For example, this could include courses on theoretical methods, data analysis, experimental techniques, or computational modelling. Please include both established topics (that will still be needed in the future) and new topics.

6. Future training requirements in aviation emissions

Following question 5, please list suggestions of key training requirements that you would expect to be provided by international associations, commercial agencies, or professional bodies. For example, this could include continuing professional development training courses on policy, legislation, or certification.

7. Highlight key areas in education or training requirements that are not currently available.

With reference to your answers to questions 3 – 6, please highlight the education or training requirements that will be high priority, but to your knowledge are not currently available (or limited availability, or not available in the local language, of education or training in this area).

8. Any other relevant information connected with future needs for education and training requirements in aviation noise and emissions.

Thank you for taking the time to complete this short questionnaire.